

IMPROVEMENTS BY SPACE ASTROMETRY (L. Lindegren)

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General accuracy

A successful mission, lasting at least 1.5 yr, is expected to yield parallaxes and relative positions and proper motions for 50 000 - 100 000 stars down to magnitude $m_{pg} = 13$, each astrometric datum with an accuracy of a few milliarcsec.

A more detailed description of expected results requires specification of instrument, mode of scanning, observing program, etc. Consider as an example the following mission model (indications of scaling properties are given when possible):

instrument : (described elsewhere). If performance is limited by diffraction or photon statistics the m.e. of any astrometric quantity scales as l^{-2} , where l is the linear size of the aperture.

scanning mode : revolving scanning with Sun/spin axis angle $\zeta = 36^\circ$. The m.e. do not depend critically on the scanning mode as long as ζ is the same; they are however roughly inversely proportional to $\sin \zeta$ for $\tilde{\omega}$, λ , and μ_λ , and almost independent of ζ for β and μ_β .

mission length : 2.5 yr. For positions and parallaxes the m.e. scales as $t^{-0.5}$, for proper motions as $t^{-1.5}$.

Then we expect the astrometric mean errors given in Table 1 for two alternative programs. The programs should be regarded as examples only, illustrating dependency on magnitude and accumulated observing time on a given object.

Program I comprises more or less the minimum set of stars necessary to set up the celestial sphere. It is obtained by dividing the sky into 51 000 areas, each of the size of the FOV ($54' \times 54'$), and selecting the brightest star in each area.

For Program II the ambition is to observe (1) all 64 000 stars down to $m_{pg} = 9.0$ and (2) an additional 36 000 stars down to $m_{pg} = 13$, selected as astrophysically interesting and/or as faint astrometric reference stars. Note that 62 % of the time is spent on the 36 % fainter stars. The absolute

maximum observing time per star is about 2400^s (sky average), which is approached for the faintest stars in this program. Thus there is little room for improving their accuracy by extending their part of the total observing time even further.

Homogeneity

The astrometric accuracy is in fact a function of position on the sky. There are fairly large systematic variations with ecliptical latitude (β) and smaller periodical variations with longitude (λ). Also, there is some anisotropy such that the latitude components of positions and proper motions are more accurate than the longitude components at low latitudes, whereas the reverse is true at the poles. The mean errors in Table 1 are sky averages; the variations with latitude are given in Table 2.

Improvement by averaging

It is of considerable interest to know how much we can possibly improve the parallax and common proper motion of a cluster by averaging the measured quantities for individual stars. The mean error $\bar{\epsilon}$ of the average of n quantities, each with m.e. ϵ , is given by

$$\bar{\epsilon}^2 = \frac{\epsilon^2}{n} (1 + (n - 1)\rho),$$

where ρ is the average correlation between any two of the quantities. As $n \rightarrow \infty$ we obtain the asymptotic mean error $\epsilon\sqrt{\rho}$. It is found that $\rho \approx 0.2$ for stars closer than $\approx 1^\circ$, decreasing to $|\rho| \leq 0.05$ for distances $\geq 4^\circ$. Thus, for extended clusters such as the Hyades it should indeed be possible to reduce the mean errors by a factor 4, whereas it seems difficult to reach even a factor 2 for less extended clusters, taking into account also the necessarily shorter observing time per star in this case.

Table 2. Relative mean errors of astrometric parameters as functions of ecliptical latitude.

β	$\Delta\lambda \cos \beta$	$\Delta\beta$	$\mu_\lambda \cos \beta$	μ_β	$\tilde{\omega}$
0°	1.8	0.9	1.8	0.9	1.2
$\pm 30^\circ$	1.3	0.8	1.3	0.8	1.1
$\pm 60^\circ$	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.7	0.8
$\pm 85^\circ$	0.3	0.8	0.3	0.8	0.4
Mean sky	1.2	0.8	1.2	0.8	1.0

Table 1. Number of stars, distribution of observing time, and expected accuracy for two alternative observing programs.

PROGRAM I							
m_{PG}	Number of stars	% of all stars on sky	Obs. time per star	% of total obs. time	Mean errors (sky averages)		
		(%)	(s)	(%)	pos.	p.m.	par.
					(10^{-3} arcsec)		
< 6	2 900	97	1010	5	0.9	1.2	1.2
6 - 7	4 700	87	1030	8	0.9	1.2	1.2
7 - 8	10 400	70	1070	19	0.9	1.2	1.3
8 - 9	16 400	40	1150	31	0.9	1.3	1.3
9 - 10	12 800	12	1290	27	1.1	1.5	1.5
10 - 11	3 600	1.2	1490	9	1.3	1.9	1.9
11 - 12	200	0.03	1740	1	1.9	2.7	2.7
12 - 13							
Total	51 000		$6 \cdot 10^7 \text{ s}$	100 %			
Average			1180 s		1.0	1.4	1.4

PROGRAM II							
m_{PG}	Number of stars	% of all stars on sky	Obs. time per star	% of total obs. time	Mean errors (sky averages)		
		(%)	(s)	(%)	pos.	p.m.	par.
					(10^{-3} arcsec)		
< 6	3 000	100	280	1	1.6	2.3	2.3
6 - 7	5 400	100	300	3	1.6	2.3	2.3
7 - 8	14 800	100	320	8	1.6	2.3	2.3
8 - 9	40 800	100	385	26	1.6	2.3	2.3
9 - 10	16 000	15	560	15	1.6	2.3	2.3
10 - 11	12 000	4	1030	21	1.6	2.3	2.3
11 - 12	6 000	0.8	1900	19	1.8	2.6	2.6
12 - 13	2 000	0.1	2100	7	3.1	4.3	4.4
Total	100 000		$6 \cdot 10^7 \text{ s}$	100 %			
Average			600 s		1.7	2.3	2.4